

CONDITIONS FOR THE FORMATION OF COMMUNITY CENTERS IN SMALL TOWNS

Rakhimov K.I.

Samarkand State Architectura – Construction
University, Republic of Uzbekistan
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Abstract: The article analyzes the conditions for the formation of public centers in small towns and their internal spatial and planning structure.

Keywords: small towns, urban planning, public centers, cultural centers, tower.

Socio-domestic factors played a significant role in the formation of the urban planning system of small cities in Uzbekistan, which in turn left its mark on the city-forming significance of the architecture of public centers, their structural-genetic typology, and architectural-artistic image.

The division of the city into small quarters was the most important event that has been preserved in places where no radical reconstruction and replanning were carried out. Many features of medieval residential and architectural-planning structures have also been preserved.

In this sense, it is impossible to give a brief interpretation of all the information collected by archaeologists, historians, ethnographers, and architects. In addition, social issues in the places we study are of great importance when considering the creation of public centers. (1) The heterogeneity of the population of small towns, class inequality, and interdependence were in most cases associated with kinship of occupations and production. This connected all families in the public center through personal ties, common interests and responsibilities, and participation in common affairs. In a word, this constituted the public center. Thus, it can be said that the unification of the population by one or another profession was the main core of the public center. This was also reflected in the name of the public center, which in some cases indicated the craft specialization of production in the public center (blacksmiths, butchers, tanners, etc.). In some cases, the public center was organized by nomads connected by family principles, which was reflected in their names (for example, Tajik or Kashgar in Tashkent, Herat, Yomini, Zamin in Samarkand). (2) The internal structure of public centers varied depending on their location. Most workshops were located in the houses of residents facing the street of the public center and at the same time served as shops. In some cases, shops and workshops were located outside the city in the public center where they were established. This is explained not by any peculiarities of the development areas unusual for the city, but by the presence of free lands around which a new public center emerged, later engaged in the same type of occupation. Public and craft associations became one of the main directions for the development of a new public center, expanding the boundaries of the city.

The increase in the quantity of goods and the improvement of living standards required new forms of organization of trade and everyday life. This situation contributed to the emergence of trade buildings and trading rows, which differed in form and size. Many of them were located near cities or public centers or were built together with them.

At the same time, not only did cities grow, but they were also divided into separate parts, synchronously with the adaptation of urban residents and the development of various cooperatives. The building areas facing the street were oriented inward. The townspeople united according to their professions, and each of them sought to have their own weapons and defend themselves against various attacks. As a result, a closed courtyard was formed with low gates, night gates, a small farmers' market, its own pool, a mosque, a school, and a public center.

In a number of cities in Central Asia, the construction of small walls bordering individual public centers can be observed. Just as a city consists of separate public complexes, public centers also consist of complexes of individual households. In this case, the city represents a monostructure of residential quarters united around a citywide public and cultural center, consisting of a complex of private houses grouped around a public center (3).

What conditions led to this and how did they influence the typology of public centers and the formation of the urban planning system? For example, let us consider the phase of the "Muslim era." Earlier pre-Islamic buildings existed as separate structures in terms of architectural and planning solutions, and in volume and environmental context they had flat roofs. Functionally, they did not represent places for large gatherings of people. The typology of the public center, as we know it, developed alongside the spread of Islam. The inner courtyard of the mosque, which had to accommodate a large number of worshippers, separate them from the noise of the city, and protect them from sun and rain, was transformed into a compact architectural structure with two or four iwans, large and small halls. The complex, including auxiliary хозяйственные buildings, a pool, a minaret, and later a madrasa and other elements, was concentrated around a single center (4).

Socio-domestic and ideological factors are reflected not only in the architectural and planning solutions of public centers but also in the development of construction programs and the creation of formal architectural forms. Craftsmen decorating the interior of buildings attempted to depict forms reflecting religious orientations, or themes connected with the glorification of rulers and the glorification of water as a source of life and fertility.

Other manifestations of the pre-Islamic period are also associated with the symbolism of water. Among them are royal animals, especially the bull as a symbol of fertility. Some images became stylized and absorbed into ornamental patterns. Floral ornaments were executed in geometric forms to express religious ideas that later flourished during that period.

Common traditions largely determined the requirements that society imposed on all its members. A person considered a member of society did not feel alone, always relying not only on material and spiritual support but also on direct assistance from the community. In addition, all members of this community could freely use the common building during public events and the shared utensils stored there — pots, bowls, tablecloths, spoons, and so on. Furthermore, items used during funeral ceremonies in this community also included several pairs of boots that were given to those who carried the coffin in cold weather. The mosque, and sometimes the madrasa, the pool, and green areas within this public building were integral parts forming a unified ensemble — the public center.

At the same time, certain requirements were imposed on each member of the community. In addition to using public spaces, residents had to ensure proper maintenance — keeping the area clean in front of their houses, maintaining water supply, and landscaping. The construction or repair of public ensembles and the cleaning of pools were also important collective works, and their rich appearance and cleanliness depended entirely on the amount of effort and money

invested by the population. Sometimes this work was carried out with the help of one of the wealthy residents, and sometimes at the expense of the common treasury. The social status of the client, financial capacity, position in society, and career were of great importance here. As the amount of money increased, the number of rooms increased, and their artistic decoration became richer. In particular, merchants and high-ranking officials invested in construction to maintain their prestige, which was considered a great benefit. As noted above, the architectural and functional solutions of such centers were strongly influenced by folk traditions and living conditions (6).

The process of construction and development of public centers itself is also interesting. If construction and reconstruction were carried out taking into account the needs of the population and the entire community, the interior decoration of the building would have a unified composition, common labor aspects, and character. The building became a product of national culture. Traditions also influenced the naming of these places. The names of public centers listed below fully confirm this point of view.

Wealthy people were also not left aside and spent their money on the needs of public centers. In addition to respect, they received the right to use free of charge what had been donated to public centers by residents of the quarter. Usually, even the relatives of the benefactor living in other quarters were involved in such expenses. If there was an entrepreneur or a prestigious person — that is, a wealthy and respected individual — his acquaintances and subordinates considered it their duty to contribute to the work carried out by this wealthy person. However, sometimes such work was financed from the common treasury.

Conclusion

Thus, the main conditions for the formation of public centers were ideological, socio-economic, and economic factors. They helped to create a new image of public centers, their appearance, and played a decisive role in the city, having a significant influence on the renewal of its compositional and environmental structure and on the territorial growth of the city.

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